

The Effect of Organizational Commitment and Organizational Culure on Employee Performance

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Abstract

The purpose of this study was to determine and analyze: (1) Organizational Commitment (2) Organizational Culture; (3) performance; and (4) the effect of organizational commitment and organizational culture on employee performance at PT Kereta Api Indonesia (KAI) West Java Regional Office, either simultaneously or partially. The research method used in this research is a descriptive survey and an explanatory survey, the unit of analysis in this study is the staff of PT Kereta Api Indonesia (KAI) West Java Regional Office with a sample of 30 people. The type of investigation is causality, and the time horizon in this study is cross-sectional.

Based on the results of the study, it was found that the Organizational Commitment of the employees of PT Kereta Api Indonesia (KAI) West Java Regional Office turned out to be a good response, Organizational Culture at PT Kereta Api Indonesia (KAI) West Java Regional Office in general can be said to be good, the performance of PT Kereta Api employees Api Indonesia (KAI) West Java Regional Office is currently considered good. Organizational Commitment and Organizational Culture simultaneously affect the performance of employees of PT Kereta Api Indonesia (KAI) West Java Regional Office. However, partially, Organizational Commitment influences employee performance more than Organizational Culture. Because Organizational Commitment is more dominant in influencing performance, it becomes the first priority in improving employee performance. then PT Kereta Api Indonesia (KAI) West Java Regional Office is advised to hold activities that can increase employee organizational commitment, so that they are able to work more professionally.

Keywords: Organizational Commitment, Organizational Culture, and performance.

1. Introduction

Local government efforts to improve the quality of public services to the community continue to be carried out by local governments. The existence of Law No. 17 of 2003 concerning state finances, which is reinforced by PP No. 8 of 2006 concerning financial reporting and performance of government agencies states that financial reporting must include information on the performance of government agencies, namely the achievements that have been achieved by budget users in relation to the budget that has been allocated. has been used. Local governments must also implement Minimum Service Standards (SPM), where services to the community must be carried out optimally. To be able to improve the quality of these services, harmony is needed between the local government, the legislature, the community and other related parties.

Performance appraisal in public organizations is very important to do, in order to improve the quality of public services. The performance appraisal is used to assess the success of the performance of a public organization in providing services to the community, because basically the orientation of public organizations is not for profit (profit oriented), but prioritizes public services (service public oriented). In addition, performance appraisal in public organizations is used as a tool to evaluate performance in the past period, to be used as a basis for formulating further corporate strategies (Srimindarti, 2004).

This condition encourages public organizations to be able to manage public services properly and responsibly. Because, if managed properly and responsibly, these public organizations will contribute income to the regional treasury, which will later become a source of regional original income (PAD). Therefore, it is necessary to manage a professional organization so as to be able to create a public organization oriented to value for money (effectiveness, efficiency, economy) (Mardiasmo, 2004). Value for money will be realized if it is supported by the commitment of all individuals in the organization or what is often called organizational commitment (Robbins, 2007). Organizational commitment is a commitment created by all individual components in carrying out organizational operations. This commitment can be realized if individuals within the organization exercise their rights and obligations in accordance with their respective duties and functions within the organization, because the achievement of organizational goals is the result of the collective work of all members of the organization. Research conducted by Kouzes (1993:32), shows that high credibility is able to produce a commitment, and only with a high commitment can a company produce good business. Organizations must give full attention and make employees believe in the organization, so that employee commitment will be obtained. If employee commitment has been obtained, employees will be loyal and able to work as well as possible for the benefit of the organization. This situation is very good for the achievement of organizational goals, because the organization has full support from its members so that they can concentrate fully on prioritized goals. Robbins and Judge (2007) define commitment as a condition in which an individual sided with the organization and its goals and desires to maintain its membership in the organization. Based on this definition, organizational commitment includes elements of loyalty to the organization, involvement in work, and acceptance of the values and goals of the organization. Where loyalty, engagement, and acceptance are related to organizational performance. Research conducted by Nurjanah (2008) suggests that organizational commitment has a positive and significant effect on employee performance. Therefore, if the organizational commitment is good, the organizational performance will be good too.

Factors that are no less important influence on organizational performance in addition to organizational commitment is organizational culture. A good organizational culture will certainly affect the quality of good public services as well. This is in accordance with the opinion of Tjiptono (2000: 75), who argues that the quality of service itself is actually influenced by many aspects, one of which is organizational culture and the way it is organized. In organizations, of course, many factors influence a person to achieve his goals, while the course of the organization is influenced by the behavior of many individuals who have their own interests. Therefore, organizational culture is very important, because it is the habits that exist in the organization. These habits regulate behavioral norms that must be followed by members of the organization, resulting in a productive culture. A productive culture is a culture that can make the organization strong and the company's goals can be achieved. Triguno (2000) argues that organizational culture is a mixture of values, beliefs and norms that are set as patterns of behavior in an organization

According to Nawawi (2003) quoted from Cushway B and Lodge D, suggests that organizational culture is a belief and values that become the main philosophy that is firmly held by organizational members in carrying out or operationalizing organizational activities. From the various definitions of organizational culture that have been stated above, it can be concluded that corporate culture is a system of values that is believed by all members of the company and which is studied, applied, and developed on an ongoing basis, functions as an adhesive system, and can be used as a reference for behavior in company to achieve the company's goals that have been set. Research conducted by Prasetyono and Kompyurini (2008), concluded that organizational culture significantly influences organizational performance. Organizational culture is very influential on the behavior of members of the organization, so that if the organizational culture is good then the members of the organization are good and quality people. And if the members are good and qualified, then the performance of the organization will be good and quality too. In the context of public organizations, performance is a measure of achievement/results in managing and running an organization which relates to all things that will, are and have been done by the organization within a certain period of time. Measurement of the performance of public organizations is important because it is useful as a reference to improve the performance of the organization to be even better in the future. Mardiasmo (2002) states that the public sector performance appraisal is carried out to fulfill three purposes, namely: (1) helping improve government performance, (2) resource allocation and decision making, (3) realizing public organizational accountability and improving institutional communication.

Many factors affect the performance of public organizations. Some of these factors are organizational commitment, and organizational culture. This is because some of these factors can improve employee performance in achieving the goals of an organization. This research refers to the research conducted by Prasetyono and Kompyurini (2008). They examine the performance of public organizations based on organizational culture, organizational commitment, and public accountability. This research does not use the public accountability variable. Mardiasmo (2002) argues that public accountability is the provision of information and disclosure of government activities and performance to parties with an interest in the report. Therefore, public accountability is a reflection / part of the performance of public organizations. If the accountability variable and the performance variable are studied together, a tautology occurs, namely the public accountability variable will assess/predict the public accountability variable itself (Jogiyanto, 2006). In other words, similar variables affect/measure similar variables (the performance of public organizations affects the performance of public organizations). Research on several factors that affect organizational performance, such as organizational commitment and organizational culture will be conducted at PT Kereta Api Indonesia (KAI) West Java Regional Office, because PT Kereta Api Indonesia (KAI) West Java Regional Office is

one of the operational parts of PT KAI's BUMN assigned to provide good public service. PT Kereta Api Indonesia (KAI) West Java Regional Office also continues to strive to be able to continue to improve its performance.

However, based on the results of preliminary observations made by researchers (Preliminary Observations, 2021) there are several deviations or phenomena relating to organizational commitment, organizational culture and employee performance at PT Kereta Api Indonesia (KAI) West Java Regional Office, which are as follows:

1. Many employees are absent from work, in the sense that they are not at work when they should. This can be seen from the complaints of the community that many services are not served.
2. Some employees feel uncomfortable and conducive office conditions, where fellow employees sometimes get involved in disagreements, fellow employees are rarely involved in working in teams so that work becomes neglected.
3. Several employees complained that the office conditions were not considered safe enough, which could be seen from the frequent loss of shoes or motorbikes when the employees worked.
4. Several employees complained that the level of incentives and compensation tended to be late, thereby reducing the employee's interest in working well.

2. Research methods

The method used in this research is the description survey and explanatory survey methods which are carried out through data collection in the field. The survey method. In the opinion of Nazir (2000), is "an investigation conducted to obtain facts from existing phenomena and seek factual information, whether about social, economic or political institutions of a group or an area". The type of investigation in this study is causality, because it will examine the causal relationship of these variables. The sample in this study were 30 employees of PT Kereta Api Indonesia (KAI) West Java Regional Office who filled out questionnaires and processed using a path analysis approach.

3. Research result

The results of the study indicate that work culture and work dicipline at work on work performance can be seen from the diagram below:

Picture. Path Analysis Calculation Results

Based on the results of the above calculations, it can be seen that

1. For the first hypothesis, t_{count} is greater than t_{table} ($2.817 > 1.68$). which means that, organizational commitment affects employee work performance
2. For the second hypothesis, t_{count} is greater than t_{table} ($2.241 > 1.68$). which means that organizational culture affects employee work performance

Then for the simultaneous effect, it can be seen organizational commitment and organizational culture on work performance together are 48.5% where 24.42% is dominated by the effect of organizational commitment on employee performance and 24.08% is the influence of organizational culture on employee work performance.

4. Discussion

The results of the above study indicate that

1. From the picture above, it can be seen that the direct contribution of organizational commitment to employee performance is 17.33% with a t_{count} coefficient of 2.817, while for the t_{table} value at the significance level (0.05) = 1.67, because the $t_{\text{count}} > t_{\text{table}}$, and not directly through the organizational culture variable by 6.89%. While the contribution of organizational commitment to employee performance as a whole reaches 24.22%, it can be concluded that organizational commitment has a significant direct effect on performance, this empirical evidence indicates that in an effort to improve employee performance, it is necessary to improve the organizational commitment paradigm factor, because organizational commitment factors are closely related. with increased performance. The path coefficient shows a positive and significant value, meaning that the better the organizational commitment of the employee, the higher the employee's performance
2. From the picture above, it can be seen that the direct contribution of organizational culture to employee performance is 17.19% with a t_{count} coefficient of 2,241, while the t_{table} value is at the significance level (0.05) = 1.67, because the $t_{\text{count}} > t_{\text{table}}$, and not directly through the organizational commitment variable by 6.89%. While the contribution of organizational culture to employee performance as a whole reached 24.08%, it can be concluded that organizational culture has a significant direct effect on employee performance, this empirical evidence indicates that in an effort to improve employee performance, it is necessary to improve organizational culture factors, because organizational culture factors are closely related. with increasing employee performance. The path coefficient shows a positive and significant value, meaning that the increasing organizational culture that is carried out will improve employee performance.

5. Conclusions and recommendations

Based on the results of research and observations that have been made, the authors would like to propose some suggestions that can be taken into consideration for PT KAI West Java Regional Office. to increase Organizational Commitment and Organizational Culture. These suggestions include:

- a. Improvement of organizational commitment by increasing the feeling of comfort while working at the institution, feeling satisfied being part of the institution, working a short span of being part of the institution, always carrying out obligations as an employee, obtaining moral goodness so that they decide to remain part of the institution and There is a balance between rights and obligations as an employee, through activities that involve all employees so that in the future it will encourage the achievement of high employee performance.

- b. Improvement of Organizational Culture by increasing the level of intensity of employees to pay attention to as much detail as possible when carrying out the work, management in the organization does not prioritize the work of employees and the organization never considers employees in making organizational decisions, so that it can trigger an increase in employee performance.
- c. The performance of PT KAI employees in the West Java Regional Office must be improved, especially regarding increasing creativity and innovation in creating competitive and comparative advantages in completing tasks, cooperation with fellow co-workers to complete work, and increasing the frequency of regular maintenance of work equipment.
- d. The priority that must be considered by PT KAI is the West Java Regional Office by optimizing work discipline in order to create premium performance.

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